

ISic3494

I.Sicily inscription 3494

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θεοδῶν

2. Φιλίππου

3. χάρε

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645115

EDR 140735

EDCS 41300104

PHI 175742

Bibliography

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo.

Sikelika 6. Palermo. At 137

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